

AI and Diplomacy: A New Era for Nuclear Arms Control

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Abstract

This in-depth analysis explains the complex implications and uses of AI technologies in influencing international security as it critically investigates the relationship between AI and nuclear arms control. The review begins by placing the difficulties surrounding nuclear arms control in context and emphasizes the critical role artificial intelligence plays in this field. The advantages and drawbacks of AI integration are carefully examined with particular reference to nuclear weapons detection, arms control agreement verification, and predictive modeling. Using both qualitative and quantitative data from primary and secondary sources, including surveys, interviews, scholarly publications, and official documents, the review uses a mixed-methods approach. To produce a thorough and exacting evaluation of the research questions, the data is analyzed using a variety of methodologies, including content analysis, statistical analysis, and scenario analysis. Including case studies on major agreements, like the START-3 agreement and the Iran nuclear deal, the review offers concrete insights into the useful application of AI in real-world scenarios. The ethical implications of AI's role in nuclear arms control are examined in detail, highlighting the necessity of putting safeguards and procedures in place to guarantee deployment that is both responsible and moral. The conclusion's summary of the main findings highlights AI's transformative potential and stresses the need to address ethical issues to ensure a more secure future for everyone on the planet. This academic investigation offers significant contributions to the current discourse on the intersection of artificial intelligence and nuclear arms control, offering insightful information to scholars, decision-makers, and interested parties.

Keywords: Foreign policy, Military, International Politics, Realism, international relations.

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